

Lung cancer championship phase V4

ID: 376e4aad-4813-47c7-a73a-f9304b8984b8

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 2536

Subjects count: 904

Age range: Between 32 years and 91 years

Sex: Male, Female, Unkown

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, SPINE, NECK, BRAIN, LUNG, WHOLEBODY, HEAD, THORAX, THORAX / ABDOMEN, THORAX INJECTE, EXTREMITY, TAP, UNKNOWN, LSPINE, CSPINE, TAP IV, TORAX, HEART, TC TOTAL BODY, TOTAL BODY, CTAP, RACHIS, TDM THORAX / ABD, TB COLLO, Unknown

Modality: CT, PT, DX